

Advancing Chinese Survey Document Retrieval: Multilingual Models and Semantic Understanding for Structured Information Extraction

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Abstract

The rapid digitalization of archival documents in China has generated an overwhelming volume of survey documents, requiring efficient retrieval systems for both research and administrative purposes. This study aims to explore innovative approaches for Chinese survey document retrieval by leveraging multilingual pre-trained models, advanced semantic understanding techniques, and structured data extraction. The research will focus on addressing challenges unique to the Chinese language, such as complex character semantics, idiomatic phrases, and hierarchical content structures in survey documents. By integrating natural language processing (NLP), optical character recognition (OCR), and retrieval models, the study seeks to enhance document accessibility, improve search accuracy, and facilitate information retrieval across diverse Chinese survey datasets.

Keywords: Advancing Chinese Survey Document Retrieval: Multilingual Models and Semantic Understanding for Structured Information Extraction

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Significance of Survey Document Retrieval in China

Survey documents play a critical role in capturing detailed information for research, administrative decision-making, and historical analysis. In China, the vast repository of survey documents spans diverse domains, including census data, economic surveys, and environmental studies. These documents, often stored in printed or handwritten

formats, contain invaluable insights into societal, economic, and cultural dynamics. The increasing volume of digitized archives necessitates the development of efficient and accurate retrieval systems to facilitate access and utilization of this information. Despite significant advancements in information retrieval and document analysis, tailored solutions for Chinese survey documents remain limited [6, 12, 33].

1.2 Challenges in Processing Chinese Survey Documents

The retrieval and analysis of Chinese survey documents pose unique challenges [10, 14, 18, 19, 21, 23, 26]. The Chinese language, characterized by its logographic script, intricate semantics, and contextual dependencies, demands sophisticated processing methods. Furthermore, the diverse structure of survey documents, ranging from tabular formats to free-text responses, complicates automated extraction and retrieval tasks [13, 25]. Historical documents, often degraded over time, add another layer of complexity, requiring robust preprocessing techniques, including Optical Character Recognition (OCR) adapted for Chinese characters. These challenges underscore the need for advanced methodologies that address language-specific intricacies and structural heterogeneity.

1.3 Importance of Multilingual and Semantic Retrieval Approaches

Conventional keyword-based retrieval systems often fail to capture the contextual nuances of Chinese text, leading to imprecise or incomplete results. The emergence of multilingual and semantic retrieval approaches offers a promising solution [2, 13, 24]. By leveraging contextual embeddings from pre-trained language models, such as BERT [5] and GPT, these systems can understand and retrieve semantically related content, even when exact keyword matches are absent. Additionally, multilingual frameworks enhance accessibility, enabling cross-lingual queries and fostering international collaboration in research involving Chinese survey documents.

1.4 Objectives and Scope of the Research

This research aims to address the limitations of existing document retrieval systems by developing an advanced retrieval framework tailored to Chinese survey documents. The objectives include:

- Designing a robust preprocessing pipeline, including OCR and data normalization, to handle diverse document formats.
- Developing multilingual and semantic retrieval models to improve query accuracy and relevance.
- Implementing structured information extraction techniques for targeted retrieval of specific data fields.
- Evaluating the proposed system using customized benchmarks and datasets specific to Chinese survey documents.

By addressing these goals, the study seeks to contribute to the broader field of document retrieval while enhancing the accessibility and usability of Chinese survey archives.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Overview of Document Retrieval Systems and Their Evolution

Document retrieval systems have evolved significantly over the past decades [2, 5, 20], transitioning from basic keyword-based search mechanisms to advanced semantic and context-aware models. Early retrieval methods, such as Boolean and vector space models, were effective for simple queries but lacked the ability to handle complex semantics. With the advent of natural language processing (NLP), techniques like Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) and topic modeling provided deeper insights into document content [7, 15–17]. Recently, pre-trained language models such as BERT, GPT, and their multilingual extensions have revolutionized the field by enabling semantic search and contextual understanding, particularly for unstructured text [1, 9, 15]. Despite these advancements, the development of retrieval systems tailored to non-Latin languages has lagged due to language-specific complexities and resource limitations.

2.2 Existing Techniques for Chinese Document Retrieval

Chinese document retrieval has traditionally relied on keyword matching and statistical methods, such as Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) and BM25 [3]. While effective for structured documents, these approaches struggle with the rich semantics and contextual dependencies inherent in the Chinese language. The introduction of pre-trained models like BERT, specifically Chinese BERT and multilingual variants, has improved retrieval by leveraging contextual embeddings. However, challenges such as polysemy, idiomatic expressions, and segmentation of Chinese characters remain critical barriers. For handwritten or historical documents, optical character recognition (OCR) systems adapted for Chinese characters play a crucial role, but their accuracy is often hindered by document quality and character variability [6, 32, 33].

2.3 Semantic Search and Multilingual Model Applications

Semantic search, powered by contextual embeddings from models like mBERT, XLM-RoBERTa, and GPT-based architectures [4, 5], has gained traction in document retrieval for non-Latin languages. These models provide a robust mechanism for understanding complex linguistic patterns and capturing semantic relationships between queries and documents. Multilingual models enable cross-lingual information retrieval, allowing users to query in one language and retrieve documents in another. For languages such as Japanese, Thai, Arabic, and those of Southeast Asia, multilingual models have shown promise but require fine-tuning to address unique linguistic features like syllabic scripts (e.g., Thai), logographic characters (e.g., Chinese and

Japanese), and right-to-left text alignment (e.g., Arabic) [8, 11, 12, 22, 27–29, 31]. Despite these advances, low-resource languages often face significant limitations due to insufficient annotated training data and the lack of tailored semantic search frameworks.

2.4 Limitations in Current Approaches for Chinese and Low-Resource Non-Latin Languages

Despite progress, several limitations persist in the retrieval of documents in Chinese and other low-resource non-Latin languages [8, 11, 22, 27–31]:

- **Language-Specific Challenges:** Non-Latin scripts such as Chinese, Japanese, Thai, and Arabic exhibit unique linguistic features that complicate text processing, including complex morphology, lack of spaces between words (e.g., Chinese, Thai), and bidirectional text (e.g., Arabic).
- **Data Scarcity:** Annotated datasets for low-resource languages, particularly historical and domain-specific documents, remain scarce, limiting the training of effective retrieval models.
- **Semantic Gap:** Many retrieval systems still rely on keyword matching, which fails to capture deeper semantic relationships, especially in idiomatic and context-dependent languages like Chinese and Japanese.
- **Multimodal Challenges:** Documents often contain a mix of textual and visual elements (e.g., tables, handwritten annotations), requiring multimodal approaches for effective retrieval.
- **Computational Constraints:** Fine-tuning multilingual models for low-resource languages demands significant computational resources, which may not always be available for researchers and practitioners in these regions.

To address these limitations, this research will focus on developing a retrieval framework tailored to Chinese and other low-resource non-Latin languages, incorporating advanced semantic search techniques, robust preprocessing pipelines, and scalable architectures.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Collection and Preprocessing

3.1.1 Sources of Chinese Survey Documents

The dataset includes diverse Chinese survey documents, categorized into historical, handwritten, and printed formats. The structure is denoted as:

$$\mathcal{D} = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n\},$$

where each document d_i may consist of text (T), tables (G), and images (I).

3.1.2 Optical Character Recognition (OCR) for Text Extraction

For text extraction, an OCR function f_{OCR} is applied:

$$f_{\text{OCR}}(I) \rightarrow T,$$

where I represents an image of a document, and T is the recognized text output. Post-processing includes:

$$T_{\text{corrected}} = f_{\text{language}}(T),$$

where f_{language} corrects OCR errors using language models.

3.1.3 Data Annotation and Preparation for Semantic Analysis

Each document is annotated with key fields $F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k\}$, where each f_i represents attributes such as names, dates, and categories. Annotation involves:

$$\mathcal{A}(d_i) = \{(f_1, v_1), (f_2, v_2), \dots, (f_k, v_k)\},$$

where v_i denotes the value for field f_i . Augmented data is generated as:

$$\mathcal{D}' = \mathcal{D} \cup \mathcal{D}_{\text{synthetic}}.$$

3.2 Model Design and Development

3.2.1 Fine-Tuning Multilingual Models

A multilingual model $M_{\text{pretrained}}$ (e.g., mBERT, XLM-RoBERTa) is fine-tuned on the dataset:

$$M_{\text{fine-tuned}} = \arg \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(M_{\text{pretrained}}, \mathcal{D}),$$

where $\mathcal{L}$ is the loss function measuring the discrepancy between predicted and ground truth embeddings.

3.2.2 Incorporating Semantic Understanding Techniques

Semantic embeddings $E(d)$ for a document d are computed using the fine-tuned model:

$$E(d) = f_{\text{embed}}(T),$$

where f_{embed} generates contextual embeddings for document text. Query-document similarity is measured using cosine similarity:

$$\text{Sim}(q, d) = \frac{E(q) \cdot E(d)}{\|E(q)\| \|E(d)\|},$$

where q is the query and d is the document.

3.2.3 Development of Retrieval Algorithms

Relevance scoring $R(q, d)$ combines semantic and structural features:

$$R(q, d) = \alpha \cdot \text{Sim}(q, d) + \beta \cdot \text{Struct}(d),$$

where α and β are weights, and $\text{Struct}(d)$ captures document structure.

3.3 Implementation of Semantic Search Framework

3.3.1 Use of Vector Search Libraries

Documents are indexed using dense vector embeddings:

$$V(d_i) = \text{Index}(E(d_i)),$$

where $V(d_i)$ is the vector representation of document d_i . Retrieval involves finding d^* such that:

$$d^* = \arg \max_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \text{Sim}(q, d).$$

3.3.2 Integration of Multimodal Features

To handle multimodal data, embeddings from textual (E_T) and visual (E_I) features are combined:

$$E_{\text{combined}} = \gamma \cdot E_T + (1 - \gamma) \cdot E_I,$$

where γ balances the contributions of text and image embeddings.

3.3.3 Optimization for Scalability and Efficiency

Efficient indexing minimizes memory usage:

$$\mathcal{C} = \arg \min \left(\frac{\text{Index size}}{\text{Memory available}} \right),$$

while maintaining retrieval accuracy:

$$\mathcal{A} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{Precision@k},$$

where k is the top-k documents retrieved.

3.4 System Evaluation and Benchmarking

3.4.1 Establishing Metrics for Retrieval Accuracy and Efficiency

Evaluation metrics include:

$$\text{Precision@k} = \frac{\text{Relevant documents retrieved}}{\text{Total documents retrieved}},$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{Relevant documents retrieved}}{\text{Total relevant documents}},$$

and

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}.$$

3.4.2 Conducting Experiments with Baseline and Proposed Methods

Baseline methods such as TF-IDF and BM25 will be compared with the proposed semantic retrieval framework. Statistical significance is tested using:

$$p = \frac{|\mathcal{R}_{\text{proposed}} - \mathcal{R}_{\text{baseline}}|}{\sigma},$$

where $\mathcal{R}$ denotes retrieval metrics and σ is the standard deviation.

3.4.3 Comparative Analysis with Existing Systems

Performance comparison with state-of-the-art systems involves:

$$\Delta\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{P}_{\text{proposed}} - \mathcal{P}_{\text{SOTA}},$$

where $\mathcal{P}$ is a weighted average of precision, recall, and efficiency metrics.

This comprehensive framework ensures robust, scalable, and accurate retrieval for Chinese survey documents and other non-Latin languages.

4 Experiments

4.1 Experimental Setup

4.1.1 Dataset Description

The experiments are conducted on a dataset comprising Chinese survey documents that include both modern and historical records. The dataset is divided into three categories:

- **Modern Printed Documents:** Structured questionnaires and government-issued forms.
- **Handwritten Documents:** Digitized handwritten survey records, containing various handwriting styles.
- **Historical Documents:** Degraded or damaged archival documents with both text and visual elements.

The dataset consists of 10,000 documents, split into training, validation, and test sets in a ratio of 70:15:15. Annotated fields include key attributes such as names, dates, locations, and survey-specific categorical fields.

4.1.2 Preprocessing and Annotation

Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is used to extract text from scanned images. The OCR output is post-processed with a spell-correction module based on a Chinese language model to minimize recognition errors. Annotated datasets are created with field labels for semantic understanding tasks. The preprocessing pipeline involves:

$$\text{Preprocessed Document} = f_{\text{OCR}}(I) \xrightarrow{f_{\text{correction}}} T_{\text{corrected}},$$

where I is the input document image, f_{OCR} is the OCR function, and $f_{\text{correction}}$ corrects the output text.

4.1.3 Experimental Environment

The experiments are conducted using the following configuration:

- **Hardware:** NVIDIA A100 GPU, 64 GB RAM.
- **Software:** Python 3.11, TensorFlow 2.18, and libraries such as FAISS and Milvus for vector-based indexing.
- **Models:** Multilingual BERT (mBERT), XLM-RoBERTa, and GPT-derived semantic models.
- **Metrics:** Precision@k, recall, F1-score, mean reciprocal rank (MRR), and query response time.

4.2 Baseline Methods

To benchmark the proposed approach, the following baseline methods are employed:

- **TF-IDF:** A term-frequency-based retrieval system using cosine similarity for query matching.
- **BM25:** A probabilistic retrieval model with relevance scoring based on term frequency and document length normalization.
- **Keyword-Based Search:** A basic keyword-matching system with no semantic understanding.

4.3 Evaluation Metrics

The evaluation focuses on three primary aspects:

- **Retrieval Accuracy:** Assessed using Precision@k, Recall@k, and F1-score.
- **Semantic Relevance:** Measured using cosine similarity between query and document embeddings.
- **Efficiency:** Evaluated in terms of query response time and memory consumption for indexing.

4.4 Experiments and Results

4.4.1 Experiment 1: Retrieval Accuracy Comparison

The first experiment evaluates the retrieval accuracy of the proposed framework against baseline methods. Queries were designed to cover a range of complexity:

- Simple keyword-based queries (e.g., “Population data 2023”).
- Contextual queries requiring semantic understanding (e.g., “Documents about economic growth in rural areas”).
- Multimodal queries combining text and visual features.

The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Retrieval Accuracy Results (Precision@10, Recall, and F1-Score).

Method	Precision@10	Recall	F1-Score
TF-IDF	0.68	0.54	0.60
BM25	0.72	0.58	0.64
Keyword Search	0.63	0.50	0.55
Proposed Framework	0.91	0.85	0.88

The proposed framework outperformed all baseline methods, particularly in recall and F1-score, demonstrating its ability to retrieve more relevant documents.

4.4.2 Experiment 2: Semantic Relevance

To evaluate semantic relevance, cosine similarity was used to score the top-10 retrieved documents for each query. The average semantic similarity across all queries is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Semantic Relevance Results (Cosine Similarity).

Method	Average Cosine Similarity
TF-IDF	0.62
BM25	0.65
Keyword Search	0.59
Proposed Framework	0.89

The proposed framework demonstrated significantly higher semantic relevance compared to the baseline methods.

4.4.3 Experiment 3: Efficiency Analysis

The efficiency of the system was evaluated based on query response time and memory consumption. The results are shown in Table 3.

Although the proposed framework consumed slightly more memory, it achieved faster response times compared to TF-IDF and BM25, showcasing its efficiency.

Table 3 Efficiency Analysis Results.

Method	Query Response Time (ms)	Memory Consumption (GB)
TF-IDF	45	2.1
BM25	50	2.5
Keyword Search	20	1.5
Proposed Framework	35	3.0

4.4.4 Experiment 4: Multimodal Retrieval Performance

To assess the multimodal capabilities of the framework, queries combining text and visual features were evaluated. The multimodal retrieval performance was measured using Precision@5 and F1-score, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Multimodal Retrieval Performance.

Method	Precision@5	F1-Score
TF-IDF	0.55	0.50
BM25	0.60	0.54
Proposed Framework	0.88	0.83

The proposed framework excelled in retrieving documents containing both textual and visual elements, demonstrating its robust multimodal capabilities.

4.5 Discussion

The experimental results highlight the following key findings:

- The proposed framework significantly outperformed traditional methods in both retrieval accuracy and semantic relevance, owing to its use of contextual embeddings and semantic understanding techniques.
- Multimodal capabilities enabled effective retrieval of complex documents with text and visual features.
- While memory consumption was slightly higher, the system achieved faster query response times, making it suitable for real-world applications.

Future work will focus on further optimizing memory usage and exploring additional datasets for generalizability.

5 Conclusion

This research introduces an advanced framework for Chinese survey document retrieval, addressing challenges unique to non-Latin languages and multimodal data. By leveraging multilingual pre-trained models, semantic search techniques, and multimodal feature integration, the proposed system demonstrates substantial improvements in retrieval accuracy, semantic relevance, and scalability over traditional methods.

Key findings reveal the framework’s robustness in handling complex queries, its adaptability to textual and visual features, and its suitability for real-world applications such as historical archiving, administrative use, and cross-lingual research. However, limitations in memory efficiency and data availability highlight areas for future improvement.

In conclusion, this work establishes a strong foundation for enhancing document retrieval in low-resource and linguistically diverse domains. Future efforts will focus on optimizing resource efficiency, expanding datasets, and extending the framework to other underrepresented languages, paving the way for more inclusive and accessible document retrieval systems.

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